

Semiconductor Nanosheets for Electrocatalytic Self-coupling of Benzaldehyde to Hydrobenzoin

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Abstract: The electrochemical reduction of biomass-derived feedstocks provides a sustainable platform for the synthesis of a wide range of chemical commodities and biofuels. Despite their interest, the optimization of reaction conditions, the screening of electrode materials, and the mechanistic understanding of these processes lag well behind other chemical routes. Here, we focus on the electrochemical self-coupling of benzaldehyde (BZH) to hydrobenzoin (HDB) using semiconductor electrocatalysts with nanosheet morphologies. By testing several semiconductor materials, a correlation is observed between their band gap and the electrochemical potential necessary to maximize selectivity towards HDB in alkaline medium, which we associate with the charge accumulation at the semiconductor surface. N-type CuInS_2 provides the highest conversion rate at $0.3 \text{ mmol cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ with a selectivity of 98.5% at $-1.3 \text{ V vs. Hg/HgO}$. Additional density functional theory calculations demonstrate a lower kinetic energy barrier at the CuInS_2 surface compared with graphitic carbon, proving its catalytic role in the self-coupling reaction of BZH.

Keywords: electrochemical reduction; self-coupling; semiconductor; benzaldehyde; hydrobenzoin, electrocatalysis, CuInS_2

1. Introduction

Biomass has huge potential as a sustainable platform for producing a wide variety of chemicals and biofuels. Through decomposition, separation, and transformation processes, biomass can be converted into its constituent molecules including polyols, carboxylic acids, furans, oxygenated aromatics, glycerol, and furfural. The addition or removal of functional groups through processes such as dehydration, deoxydehydration, hydrodeoxygenation, hydrogenolysis, or decarboxylation can upgrade the product, increasing its value.[6-8]

The conversion of biomass-derived products into chemical commodities through electrochemical routes offers numerous advantages over alternative strategies. Electrocatalytic reactions can make efficient use of renewable energies such as solar and wind to drive the chemical reaction under ambient pressures and temperatures, often without the need for additional reductive or oxidative reagents.[1-5] Besides, the combination of renewable electricity sources with biomass-derived precursors instead of fossil fuels allows processes with net zero carbon emissions.

While significant progress has been made in recent years in the development of electrocatalysts and processes for several small molecule reactions, such as hydrogen, carbon dioxide, nitrogen, and oxygen reactions,[9-12] the enormous potential of electrochemical processes to produce a wide range of other chemicals has yet to be realized.

Some efforts have been dedicated to exploring the electrochemical reduction of biomass-derived carbonyls, including furfural, 5-hydroxymethylfurfural, and benzaldehyde (BZH) to monomer alcohol. [13, 14] For example, the BZH hydrogenation product, benzyl alcohol (BA), is a chemical commodity used as a solvent in the fields of printing and coating, and as an additive in the fragrance industry.[15] Another important carbonyl electroreduction process is

dimerization, which shows potential for the production of fuels,[16] such as hydrofuroin (HDF) and hydrobenzoin (HDB). HDB is also an important industrial chemical as a structural motif in antiepileptic drugs and photo-initiators.[17]

As shown in scheme 1, it is generally accepted that the electrochemical hydrogenation of carbonyl to monomer alcohols takes place through a proton-coupled electron transfer path (PCET).[17-19] Li's group has shown the rate-limiting step of carbonyl electrochemical hydrogenation follows a Langmuir-Hinshelwood (L-H) mechanism, while dimer formation of pinacol from carbonyl groups occurs via radical-radical self-coupling.[20-22] Schröder's work also suggested that pinacol is formed through radical self-coupling via electro-tunneling without reactant adsorbed.[23] These two pathways compete with the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER).

Scheme 1. (a) Proposed pathways of electrochemical reduction of carbonyls and the competing HER; (b) Proposed mechanism of two different pathways for monomer alcohol and pinacol products.

In terms of electrode materials, Zhang's group screened a series of electrocatalysts towards self-coupling reactions, finding that, aside from carbon, Ti, In, and Au provide the best coupling selectivities, while also blocking the HER.[24] Other reported elements showing activity for the electroreductive carbonyl coupling reaction are Pb, Zn, Cu, and Sn.[25] One common characteristic among these elements is their limited capacity for hydrogen adsorption.[16] Besides, these elements form stable semiconductor sulfide compounds that are used in a range of applications. Thus, we considered exploring their performance as electrocatalysts for the self-coupling reaction of BZH.

In recent years, some two-dimensional (2D) metal chalcogenide semiconductors have demonstrated excellent potential for several applications, including electro- and photo-catalysis, in part related to their distinctive crystal phases and morphologies.[26, 27] While compared to metals, semiconductor materials are generally considered less ideal electrocatalysts because of their low carrier densities,[28, 29] their tunable space charge layer (SCL) and the self-gating effect recently reported for nanosheet[30] semiconductors can overcome these limitations. Lam's group explored the use of MoS₂ in the electrocatalytic hydrogenation and dimerization of furfural.[18] They found that the octahedral MoS₂ structure (1T phase), exhibiting metallic properties, promotes the production of mono-alcohols, while the semiconducting hexagonal MoS₂ structure (2H phase) showed higher selectivity towards dimer formation.

Herein, we explore the use of 2D semiconductor electrocatalysts to drive the BZH coupling reaction to HDB. Different metal chalcogenide semiconductors (CuInS₂, Cu_{1.8}S, In_{2.77}S₄, ZnIn₂S₄, and Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S) with nanosheet morphology are synthesized and the effect of pH and voltage on their BZH self-coupling performance is analyzed. We further correlate the process selectivity with the applied voltage and space charge layer formed in the different semiconductor materials. Besides experimentally characterizing the charge transport properties,

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations are also employed to determine the reaction steps free energy on graphitic carbon and the best performance semiconductor material CuInS₂.

2. Experimental sections

2.1 Materials synthesis

2.2. *Chemicals*: Copper(I) chloride (CuCl, Sigma Aldrich), indium(III) chloride (InCl₃, Sigma Aldrich), zinc acetate (Zn(CH₃COO)₂, Sigma Aldrich), thiourea (CH₄N₂S, Sigma Aldrich), ethylene glycol (Thermo Scientific™), cadmium acetate (Cd(CH₃COO)₂, Sigma Aldrich), ammonia solution (NH₃·H₂O 25%~28%, Sigma Aldrich), ethanol, benzaldehyde (BZH, Sigma Aldrich), benzyl alcohol (BA, Sigma Aldrich), benzoic acid (BZA, Sigma Aldrich), and hydrobenzoin (HDB, Sigma Aldrich) were used as purchased, without further purification

2.2.2 *Synthesis of CuInS₂*: 0.4 mmol CuCl, 0.4 mmol InCl₃, and 1.6 mmol thiourea were dissolved into 40 mL ethylene glycol, the mixture was then transferred into a 50 mL Teflon-lined reactor, which was put in an oven and heated at 200 °C for 12 h. The black precipitate was collected by centrifugation, washed with water and ethanol several times, and dried at 60 °C overnight in an oven.

2.1.3 *Synthesis of Cu_{1.8}S*: Cu_{1.8}S was prepared using a similar method as the one used to produce CuInS₂ but using only 0.4 mmol of CuCl as the metal precursor.

Synthesis of In_{2.77}S₄: In_{2.77}S₄ was prepared using a similar method as the one used to produce CuInS₂ but using only 0.4 mmol of InCl₃ as the metal precursor.

2.1.4 *Synthesis of ZnIn₂S₄*: 1 mmol Zn (CH₃COO)₂, 1 mmol InCl₃ and 6 mmol thiourea were uniformly dissolved into 40 mL H₂O. The mixture was then transferred into a 50 mL Teflon-lined reactor, which was put in an oven and heated at 200 °C for 20 h. The light-yellow

precipitate was collected by centrifugation, washed with water and ethanol several times, and dried at 60 °C overnight in an oven.

2.1.5 Synthesis of Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S: 2 mmol Zn (CH₃COO)₂ and 2 mmol Cd (CH₃COO)₂ were put into a three-necked round-bottom flask. Then 14 mL MQ-water was added. After heating to 80 °C and maintaining 0.5 h with stirring, 2 mL NH₃·H₂O and 500 mg thiourea were added into. keeping reflowing and stirring for 6 h. The yellow precipitate was collected by centrifugation, washed with water and ethanol several times, and dried at 60 °C overnight in an oven.

2.2 Materials characterization

The morphology of the samples was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) in a Zeiss Auriga microscope (Carl Zeiss, Jena, Germany) with an energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) detector at 20 kV to analyze the composition of the sample. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was carried out using a ZEISS LIBRA 120, operating at 120 kV. Scanning TEM (STEM) and high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) were carried out under the 200 keV Tecnai F20 field emission microscope. Electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) and high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) STEM were carried out using a Gatan Quantum image filter embedded in the F20 (S)TEM. Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were collected at 40 kV and 40 mA with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). Characterization of the surface composition and the valence of elements was done by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) conducted on a Thermo Scientific K-Alpha+ with Mono Al K α radiation. The energy, voltage, and beam current were 1486.6 eV, 12KV, and 6 mA, respectively. Inductively coupled plasma mass spectroscopy (ICP-MS) was tested on 7800 ICP-MS from Agilent Technologies. The solid ultraviolet–visible (UV-Vis) spectroscopy absorbance characterization was carried out on Perkin Elmer Lambda 950 UV/vis/MR.

2.3 Product quantification and calculation

High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) on an Agilent 1200 series at 25 °C was used to analyze the organics. The HPLC was equipped with an ultraviolet-visible detector and 4.6 mm×150 mm Shim-pack GWS 5µm C18 column. The eluting solvents of A: 5 mM ammonium formate aqueous solution; solution B: acetonitrile was utilized. The program is 60% solution B and 40% solution A for 11 min. The flow rate is 0.5 mL s⁻¹. The injection amount is 1 µl. The calibration curves of standard chemicals were employed to determine and quantify the products. The total conversion and selectivities were calculated using the following equations. It should be mentioned that ~0.5 mM per 20 mM BZH was oxidized to BZA, which was deducted when calculating the results.

$$\text{Conv} = \frac{\text{moles of BZH consumed}}{\text{initial moles of BZH}} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Sel}_{\text{BA}} = \frac{\text{ratio of BA}}{\text{conversion ratio amount of BZH}} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Sel}_{\text{HDB}} = \frac{2 \times \text{ratio of HDB}}{\text{conversion ratio amount of BZH}} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Sel}_{\text{BZA}} = \frac{\text{ratio of BZA}}{\text{conversion ratio amount of BZH}} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Sel}_{\text{others}} = 100\% \times \left(1 - \frac{\text{ratio of BZA} + 2 \times \text{ratio of HDB} + \text{ratio of BZA}}{\text{conversion ratio amount of BZH}} \right) \quad (5)$$

2.4 Density functional theory (DFT) calculation of free energy.

All DFT calculations were performed using the Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP), employing the projected augmented wave revising Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof function (PAW–PBE). The cutoff energy was set at 500 eV for all the geometry optimizations. A 2 × 2 × 1 Monkhorst–Pack grid and A 4 × 3 × 2 Monkhorst–Pack grid were used to obtain the surface calculations on the Graphite carbon system and the CuInS₂ system, respectively. At least a 20

Å vacuum layer was applied in the z-direction of the slab models, preventing vertical interactions between slabs. The adsorption energy (E_{ads}) is described by equation 4 where $E_{(substrate/product \text{ and } graphite \text{ carbon})}$, $E_{(substrate/product)}$ and $E_{(graphite \text{ carbon})}$ are the energies of the system involving the Graphite carbon surface connecting the substrate/product, the only substrate/product, and the Graphite carbon surface, respectively. All structures were completely relaxed until the force on each atom was less than $0.01 \text{ eV } \text{Å}^{-1}$.

$$E_{ads} = E_{(substrate/product \text{ and } graphite \text{ carbon})} - E_{(substrate/product)} - E_{(graphite \text{ carbon})} \quad (4)$$

The free energy (E_{free}) was calculated using equation 5,6 where the free energy phase of each adsorbent is calculated taking $*phCHO \rightarrow *phCHOH$ species.

$$E_{free*phCHO \rightarrow *phCHOH} = E_{free*phCHOH} - E_{free*phCHO} - E_{free*H} \quad (5)$$

$$E_{free*2phCHOH \rightarrow *HDB} = E_{free*HDB} - 2 E_{free*phCHOH} \quad (6)$$

2.5 Electrocatalytic tests

The electrochemical performance of the electrocatalyst was evaluated on Corrtest CS2350 EIS Bipotentiostat (2-channel, Wuhan Corrtest Instrument Corp., Ltd) using a 3-electrodes system in an H-cell reactor divided by Nafion 117 proton exchange membrane. The working electrode was prepared as follows: 6 mg powder was dispersed into 500 μL H_2O , 480 μL ethanol, and 80 μL 5% Nafion solution. The solution was dropped on a $2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^2$ carbon cloth ($\sim 1.5 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{cm}^{-2}$) that was then cut into $2 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ pieces. Platinum mesh and Ag/AgCl (KCl saturated) or Hg/HgO as counter electrode and reference electrode, respectively.

2.5.1 Sodium acetate-acetic acid solution (pH=5.3): Cyclic voltammetry was tested in the range 0.2 V \sim -0.9 V (vs. Ag/AgCl.) For the I-t curve, -1.1 V (vs. Ag/AgCl) was applied as a constant voltage.

2.5.2 Potassium carbonate-potassium bicarbonate solution (pH=9.0): Cyclic Voltammetry was

tested in the range -0.8 V ~ -1.3 V (vs. Hg/HgO). For the I-t curve, we applied -1.2 V (vs. Hg/HgO) as the constant voltage.

2.5.3 1 M KOH solution (pH=14): Cyclic Voltammetry was tested -0.8 V ~ -1.3 V (vs. Hg/HgO). EIS was conducted at -1.2 V (vs. Hg/HgO). For the I-t curve, applied -1.2 V or -1.0 V ~ -1.6 V (vs. Hg/HgO) as constant voltage and conducted 2 h. The impedance-potential (IMPE) tests were applied among open circle potential ± 0.5 V with different frequencies.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Structural, crystalline, and chemical properties of semiconductor materials

Several different metal sulfide semiconductors (CuInS₂, Cu_{1.8}S, In_{2.77}S₄, ZnIn₂S₄, and Zn_{0.5}Cd_{0.5}S) were produced from the reaction of metal chlorides (copper(I) chloride and indium (III) chloride) or acetates (zinc acetate and cadmium acetate) with thiourea under solvothermal reaction at 200 °C or ambient pressure at 80 °C.

CuInS₂ (CIS) is an n-type semiconductor with a direct bandgap of 1.5 eV.[31] The CIS obtained by a solvothermal method displayed a nanosheet morphology with a thickness of ~ 50 nm (Figure 1a-b). Its X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern displayed a peak at 28.03° corresponding to the (2 1 1 2) phase of CuInS₂ (Figure S1b). From the crystalline domain in Figure 1c, the CuInS₂ lattice fringe distances were measured to be 0.335 nm, 0.333 nm, and 0.334 nm, at 59.49° and 119.88° which could be interpreted as the hexagonal CuInS₂ phase, visualized along its [0001] zone axis. Electron energy loss spectroscopy (EELS) chemical composition maps show Cu, In, and S to be homogeneously dispersed throughout the whole material (Figures 1d and S1c-f). The elemental ratio was Cu:In:S = 1:1.3:2.5 according to energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) results (Table S1), Cu:In:S = 1:0.57:1.77 according to X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) data, and Cu:In:S = 1:1.36:2.18 as tested by ICP-MS (Tables S1-3). These results point

at a copper-rich surface.

$\text{Cu}_{1.8}\text{S}$ (CS) is a p-type semiconductor with a bandgap of 1.29 eV.[32] CS synthesized using a solvothermal method showed a nanosheet-based architecture with 50 nm-thick plates (Figure S2a-b). XRD analysis confirmed its rhombohedral digenite structure PDF# 047-1748 (Figure S2c). The Cu/S elemental ratio was $\text{Cu/S} = 1.8$ when determined by EDS analysis, matching well the digenite phase (Table S1), $\text{Cu/S} = 1.7$ according to XPS data (Figure S2d-f, Table S2), and $\text{Cu/S} = 1.35$ according to ICP-MS data (Table S3), denoting a sulfur-rich surface.

$\text{In}_{2.77}\text{S}_4$ (IS) is a p-type semiconductor with a direct bandgap of 2.0 ~2.3 eV.[33] IS particles resembling a nanoflower composed of multiple nanosheets were synthesized using a solvothermal method (Figure S3a-b). Their thickness was estimated at 50 nm and their XRD pattern matched that of the cubic $\text{In}_{2.77}\text{S}_4$ phase (PDF# 088-2495). EDS analysis showed their elemental composition to be $\text{In/S} = 0.59$ (Table S1), $\text{In/S} = 0.82$ according to XPS (Figure S3d-f, Table S2), which matched with ICP-MS data at $\text{In/S} = 0.56$ (Table S3).

ZnIn_2S_4 (ZIS) is a n-type semiconductor with a direct bandgap of 2.5 eV for the hexagonal phase.[34] ZIS obtained by a solvothermal method displayed a cross-linked nanosheet-based architecture with a nanosheet thickness of ~50 nm (Figure S4a). XRD analysis confirmed its hexagonal ZnIn_2S_4 phase (PDF# 03-065-2023, Figure S4b). EDS analysis showed their elemental ratio to be $\text{Zn:In:S} = 1:1.4:3.2$ (Table S1), $\text{Zn:In:S} = 1:1.9:2.3$ according to XPS data (Figure S4c-f, Table S2), while ICP-MS quantified their composition at $\text{Zn:In:S} = 1:1:2.2$ (Table S3).

Finally, $\text{Zn}_{0.5}\text{Cd}_{0.5}\text{S}$ (ZCS), which is a solid solution of CdS and ZnS, is a n-type semiconductor with a direct bandgap of 2.51 eV.[35] ZCS was obtained at ambient pressure and 80 °C and it was characterized by a nanosheet-based morphology with a sheet thickness of ~30 nm (Figure S5a). The XRD pattern matched that of cubic CdS PDF# 089-0440 and cubic ZnS PDF# 05-

0566 phases (Figure S5b). The composition was Zn:Cd:S = 1:1.2:2.4 as determined by EDS analysis (Table S1) and Zn:Cd:S = 1:0.45:2.4 as determined by XPS (Figure S5d-f, Table S2), Zn:Cd:S = 1:1:2.4 determined by ICP-MS analysis (Table S3) and thus showing a Zn-rich surface.

Figure 1. CIS structural and chemical characterization: (a) SEM image. (b) TEM image. (c) HRTEM image showing the structure of the nanosheets. The inset shows the indexed power spectrum (FFT) obtained at the orange squared area in the HRTEM image. (d) EELS chemical composition maps from the red squared area of the STEM micrograph. Individual Cu $L_{2,3}$ -edges at 931 eV (red), In $M_{4,5}$ -edges at 443 (green), S $L_{2,3}$ -edges at 165 eV (blue), and composites of Cu-In, Cu-S, and Cu-In-S.

3.2 Electrocatalytic performance

All catalysts were supported on graphitic carbon cloth (CC) with a working electrode area of $2 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ and a loading of $\sim 1.5 \text{ mg cm}^{-2}$. The electrochemical performance of the different semiconductors towards the reduction of 20 mM BZH was initially tested under different pH aqueous solutions at a working potential of -0.6 V vs. RHE for 2 h (Figure 2).

In sodium acetate buffer solution (pH 5.2), the BZH conversion was relatively low for all the semiconductors, being BZA the main product. Only CS produced a slight amount of BA (Figure 2a). When comparing the cyclic voltammetry (CV) curves obtained in the presence and absence of 20 mM BZH at pH 5.2 (Figure S6), we observe moderate differences for all the catalysts, which points to low catalytic performance in these reaction conditions.

When increasing the pH to 9.0 with a potassium carbonate-bicarbonate buffer solution, the BZH conversion slightly increased and the selectivity to HDB sharply improved (Figure 2b). From the comparison of the CV curves in the presence and absence of 20 mM BZH at pH 9.0 (Figure S7), we observe the presence of BZH to strongly increase the current density and reduce the reaction overpotential for all the materials.

The use of a 1M KOH electrolyte, i.e. increasing the pH to 14, significantly improved the conversion. The selectivity towards HDB also increased for some of the materials, reaching values above 95% for all the catalysts (Figure 2c). Besides, when comparing the CV curves in the presence and absence of BZH, the onset potential for all catalysts further decreased in absolute value and the semicircle in the Nyquist plot of the EIS greatly shrunk, which correlates with an improved charge transport at the electrode/electrolyte interphase (Figure S8).

Figure 2. Products of the electroreduction of BZH after 2 h reaction on the different catalysts tested. Electrolyte compositions: 1 M sodium acetate buffer solution (pH 5.3) (a); 1 M potassium carbonate bicarbonate buffer solution (pH 9) (b) and 1 M KOH aqueous solution (pH 14) (c) at working potentials -1.1 V vs. Ag/AgCl; -1.2 V vs. Hg/HgO -1.4 V vs. Hg/HgO; (\sim -0.6 V vs. RHE), respectively.

Among the different catalysts tested, CIS showed the best performance toward HDB production from BZH, with a BZH conversion of 99.83% and an HDB selectivity of 98.46%. Notice that in 1M KOH electrolyte, BZH spontaneously transforms to BZA and BA with 100% selectivity (50% selectivity to BZA and 50% to BA) when no potential is applied (Figure S9). The application of a voltage speeds up the reaction and shifts its selectivity toward HDB in an alkaline environment.

Figures 3a and S10-S14 show the conversion and product selectivity after a 2 h reaction at different potentials for all the different catalysts. For CIS, when increasing the absolute value of the applied potential, the selectivity towards HDB initially increased and later decreased at too high negative potentials (Figure 3a and Table S4). The selectivity toward HDB reached a maximum of 98.46% at -1.3 V vs. Hg/HgO. The other catalysts showed a similar trend, except for CS which showed no maximum selectivity toward HDB. Notably, graphitic carbon showed

notable performance, with selectivities up to 98% for the coupling reaction and conversion just below 95%, consistent with previous reports that associated this characteristic with the ability of graphite to promote radical generation.[24, 36]

Figure 3b shows the time-dependent conversion/selectivity at -1.3 V vs. Hg/HgO on CIS. The BZH concentration gradually decreases and the concentration of HDB gradually increases. The reaction rate on CIS was estimated at $0.3 \text{ mmol cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$, well above that of CC ($0.13 \text{ mmol cm}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$, Figure S15).

The CIS stability upon cycling was also tested. Figures S16 and S17 show the performance obtained in 5 consecutive 2 h I-t curve cycles, using the same electrode but replacing the electrolyte at each cycle. Within each cycle, the current slightly decreases as the reactants are consumed. However, when refreshing the electrolyte, the conversion and selectivity towards HDB are recovered in the five cycles. Besides, SEM characterization of the sample after cycling (Figure S18) shows the nanosheet structure to be partially transformed into smaller particles with a fine nanostructured surface.

To better determine the role of BA, CV curves of CIS with different substrates were measured. As shown in Figure 3c, when adding 10 mM BZH + 10 mM BA into the electrolyte, the current density decreased over that obtained with 20 mM BZH. This decrease was more accentuated when adding just 20 mM BA. EIS data (Figure 3d) also showed the charge transfer resistance in the presence of 20 mM BZH ($\sim 3.0 \Omega$) to be lower than that obtained with a combination of 10 mM BZH + 10 mM BA ($\sim 3.2 \Omega$), although both showed a relatively fast charge transfer rate compared with a pure 1 M KOH electrolyte ($\sim 75 \Omega$) and an electrolyte containing 20 mM BA ($\sim 75 \Omega$). Besides, the time-dependent transformation of 10 mM BZH + 10 mM BA and 20 mM BA over CIS in pH 14 at -1.3 V vs. Hg/HgO was measured and displayed in Figure 3f. We observe a minor conversion of BA in both cases. From these experimental results, we conclude

that BA could not be activated into a radical to yield HDB, and the presence of BZH was required to yield HDB.

Figure 3. (a) Potential-dependent conversion (conv.%) and selectivity (sel.%) over CIS in pH 14 (1 M KOH); (b) Time-dependent transformation of 20 mM BZH over CIS at -1.3 V vs. Hg/HgO. (c,d) CV curves (c) and Nyquist plots (d) of the CIS electrode with and without organics; (e) Time-dependent transformation of 10 mM BZH and 10 mM BA over CIS in pH 14 and at -1.3 V vs. Hg/HgO; (f) Time-dependent transformation of 20 mM BA over CIS in pH 14 at -1.3 V vs. Hg/HgO.

3.3 Relationships between semiconductor materials properties with performance.

Upon immersing a semiconductor into an electrolyte, the interphase reaches equilibrium when the Fermi level (E_F) at the semiconductor surface matches the chemical potential of the redox couple (E_R) in the solution. Thus, a space charge layer (SCL) with a modified carrier concentration and bent electronic bands is formed at the semiconductor side of the interphase. In thin enough semiconductors, this SCL extends over the whole material. The flat band potential (E_{fb}) is the potential that needs to be applied to the semiconductor to equilibrate the interface E_F so there is no SCL at the junction between the semiconductor and the electrolyte. Thus, E_{fb} depends not only on the semiconductor properties but also on the electrolyte

composition.

The E_F of an n-type semiconductor is generally higher than E_R (for this self-coupling reaction, normally E_R is located at 0 V vs. RHE.[37, 38]). Thus, when immersing an n-type semiconductor into an electrolyte, to reach an equilibrium, free electrons are transferred to the solution and an upward band bending at the surface of a bulk semiconductor or a downshift of the Fermi level for a thin semiconductor layer is obtained (Figure 4). In this case, the generated SCL is depleted of electrons and provides a barrier for electrons to be transferred from the semiconductor into the electrolyte. When applying a negative voltage, that is shifting upwards the potential at the semiconductor surface in contact with the CC electrode, the band bending decreases (E_F increases) up to a point when the E_{fb} is reached. At even more negative potentials, the bands bend downwards (E_F shifts upwards) generating an accumulation layer and eventually forming a degenerated layer with a metallic character.[28, 39, 40] Liu et al. observed the electronic conductivity of thin enough semiconductors to strongly increase with the applied electrochemical potential and described this phenomenon as a self-gating effect.[30]

In the case of a p-type semiconductor, when immersed into the electrolyte, if the E_F is below the E_R , holes are injected into the solution and a hole depletion layer is formed at the interface. To reach the E_{fb} , a positive potential needs to be applied at the CC/semiconductor interface. If applying a negative potential, an increased band bending reinforces the hole depletion layer near the surface of the semiconductor. This depletion layer becomes wider and impedes the flow of holes into the electrolyte. At highly negative potentials, the bands may bend to a point where the valence band edge aligns with the E_R of the electrolyte. This alignment creates a condition known as inversion, where the surface region of the p-type semiconductor becomes n-type in nature. In this case, the surface can become conductive.

Figure 4. Effect of varying the applied potential on the band bending. E_F and d_{sc} are the Fermi energy and thickness of the space charge layer formed in the semiconductor, respectively.

Ultraviolet–visible (UV-vis) spectroscopy (Figure S19a-e) and Mott-Schottky analyses (Figure S20a-e) were used to determine the band gap and E_{fb} of the different electrodes after immersion in pH 14 solution. The obtained results are summarized and related to the potential of maximum BZH-to-HDB selectivity in Figure 5 and Table S5. For n-type ZCS, showing the largest band gap and the largest absolute value of E_{fb} among the tested materials, the BZH-to-HDB conversion at all the potentials applied is the lowest, ZCS required -1.5 V vs. Hg/HgO to reach its peak performance. In contrast, n-type CIS required just -1.3 V vs. Hg/HgO to reach its peak performance. Notably, when applying -1.6 V vs. Hg/HgO on CIS, both the selectivity and conversion of BZH-to-HDB decreased, which we associated with an HER increase. For p-type CS, when applying a negative potential of -1.3 V vs. Hg/HgO the conversion was lower than that of CIS. Overall, we observed the potential of the maximum BZH-to-HDB selectivity to increase with E_{fb} and to decrease with the semiconductor band gap. We associate this

experimental result with the applied potential having to be lower than E_{fb} for a proper concentration of electrons to accumulate on the space charge layer and reach an optimal thickness for the formation of HDB. When applying a too high negative potential, a too large excess of electrons at the semiconductor surface induces a buildup of the amount of adsorbed hydrogen and substrate that results in the favored formation of monomer alcohols over dimers as the reaction product.

Figure 5. Illustration of band edges, E_{fb} , and the applied potential providing the highest sel.% for each of the semiconductor materials, ZCS, ZIS, IS, CIS, and CS.

The electroreduction of BZH in acidic conditions might take place as follows (* = active site):[41]

Equations (1)-(6) correspond to the formation of BZH, while equations (1)-(5) and (7) correspond to the formation of HDB.

On the other hand, the electroreduction of BZH in alkaline media most likely follows (• = radical specie): [24]

Equations (1), (8)-(10) and (6) correspond to the formation of BZH, while equations (1), (8)-(12) correspond to the formation of BZH.

To obtain monomer alcohol, the adsorption of hydrogen and substrate, a low pH electrolyte and a high H adsorption ability of the anode material are required,[21, 42] and at least one electron needs transfer to H. On the other hand, coupling products are more easily obtained at higher pH and on materials having poor H adsorption abilities, where the electron directly transfers to the substrate.

Figure 6. Free energy profiles for the self-coupling reaction process from BZH to HDB on CIS and graphic carbon. * Represents an adsorption site.

Previous in situ Raman spectroscopy measurements by C. Liu et al. show that the in-plane aromatic C–H bending peaks of BZH change upon adsorption on carbon fiber paper, while the peak assigned to the C–O stretching vibration in carbonyl group C=O remains unchanged.[24] When applying a relatively low voltage, the C–O peak disappears, which is explained by considering that upon increasing the electronic concentration at the electrode surface, C=O with higher electron cloud density tends to move away, while the phenyl ring center with low electron density tends to adsorb more strongly. Therefore, according to previous investigations, to explain the excellent performance of CuInS₂, we considered the BZH adsorption through the phenyl ring.

While graphitic carbon has a notable BZH electroreduction performance, the CIS-based electrode displays significantly higher conversion rates. To investigate the favorable effect of CIS at the atomic surface level, we explored the free energy changes from the substrate BZH, to the ketyl intermediate BZH-H₂O, BZH-H, and the product HDB using DFT calculations (Figures. S21-22). Figure 6 displays the free energy profiles for CIS and graphite, assuming the

BZH adsorption through the phenyl ring. DFT results demonstrate that while the proton transfer and the coupling steps show little difference, the substrate BZH shows a much higher affinity for CIS (-4.98 eV) than for graphite carbon (-0.03 eV), and the splitting of H₂O into H (3rd step in Figure 6) is much favored on CIS (+1.87 eV) than on C (+4.71 eV). The significant difference between carbon and CIS in adsorption energy of the phenyl group of BZH is related to the stronger d- π interactions between d-orbitals of transition metal of Cu with π electrons of phenyl ring than π - π stacking interactions between phenyl rings.[43] This improved adsorption is essential to promote the BZH conversion on CIS. On the other hand, the adsorption enhancement might also facilitate the splitting of H₂O into H attached to O=C of BZH converted into the ph(OH)CH radical. To further clarify the active site toward the BZH to HDB reaction, we computed the BZH adsorption energy on Cu and In sites within their sulfides (Figure S23), showing Cu to provide a stronger binding, consistently with previous literature.[43]

4. Conclusion

A series of semiconductor materials with nanosheet morphology were explored as electrocatalysts for the BZH self-coupling reaction to HDB. While the conversion rate strongly increased with pH, the selectivity towards HDB was strongly related to the applied potential. Conversions up to 99.83% and HDB selectivity of 98.46% were obtained using CIS at -1.3V vs. Hg/HgO. We further analyzed the relationship between the semiconductor band gap and E_{fb} and the potential required to maximize selectivity. Applying negative potential lower than E_{fb} on n-type semiconductors, the electrons accumulate on the surface to reach the optimized condition towards the electro-reductive reaction BZH-to-HDB. Meanwhile, DFT-based computational simulations further indicated that the kinetic energy barrier of the BZH self-coupling reaction on CIS is lower than on graphitic carbon, which is associated with the much higher affinity of BZH for CIS and the favored splitting of H₂O into H on CIS when compared

to C.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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